

ABOVE AND MINIMUM: A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE MENTAL HEALTH AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG WAGE EARNERS

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Above and Minimum: A Comparative Study on the Mental Health and Job Satisfaction among Wage Earners

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Abstract

This study examines mental health and job satisfaction with work in above- and minimum wage earners. Similar findings show low mental health for both income scales. All income brackets show some concern, though not much higher than average. Depression is slightly higher among those earning above the minimum wage. Both income groups struggle with behavioral control, suggesting that concentrated interventions may improve coping and stress management. Lower levels of positive affect emphasize the importance of workplace emotional well-being regardless of income. The research suggests that above-minimum wage and minimum wage mental health are not statistically different. The report shows that job satisfaction is good across income brackets. Average job satisfaction is marginally higher for those earning above minimum wage. This group exhibits greater intrinsic job satisfaction, an indication of life contentment, suggesting a tendency for income and intrinsic job satisfaction to increase together. Earning above the minimum wage promotes extrinsic satisfaction, or non-work-related contentment. The study concluded that both intrinsic and extrinsic factors contribute to a productive workplace, emphasizing the need of considering issues beyond monetary compensation. The findings from this study will contribute to analyzing mental health and job satisfaction differences between above minimum wage earners and minimum wage earners.

Keywords: *mental health, job satisfaction, above and minimum wage earners, emotional well-being, life contentment*

Introduction

The day-to-day lives of the typical Filipino have become increasingly challenging given the current state of affairs. With taxes and high prices, it may be difficult for certain individuals to keep their finances stable, especially if they need to pay for their own transportation to get to work (Cantimbulan, 2023). According to Katigbak (2022), there has been a noticeable disparity in the quantity of work people do compared to their pay over the last few months. This hasn't been a problem for the past few months. Pay in the Philippines has been an issue for the last two years, even prior to the pandemic. Now that there was a rising inflation and another recession in the works, it is a much greater worry.

The health state of a person is not only about physical health but also mental health. The World Health Organization (2019) stated that the state of well-being in which an individual became aware of his or her own abilities, can overcome the normal stresses of life, can work creatively, and is able to benefit in the community is mental health. Thus, society should regard mental health as a source of human capital or well-being. For people to thrive, take care of themselves, and interact with others, they all need to have excellent mental health, thus it's critical to address their needs and recognize the intrinsic value of that health.

Due to the current working environment, a variety of businesses and institutions are facing difficulties. Employers believed that the working environment was the most important factor to take into account for increased job satisfaction (Taheri et al., 2020). In addition to that Lu et al. (2019), eloquently stated that the factors that determine job satisfaction have been identified as duty period, job performance, loyalty, effort, leadership, and reward. Thus, when job satisfaction was taken into account, meaningful work had a negative relationship with depression, but it didn't have much of a relationship with anxiety and stress. In the same way, job satisfaction was a poor indicator of depression and stress. Also, the links between productive work and both anxiety and stress were tempered by how satisfied people were with their jobs. In particular, only people who thought their jobs were important and satisfying said they had less anxiety and stress (Allan et al., 2016). Psychological factors and job stress had a negative impact on various aspects of work life, particularly job satisfaction. According to studies, stress had a negative impact on job satisfaction and that it increased tardiness, absenteeism, and even job abandonment. Organizational commitment had also decreased by reducing job stress (Singh et al., 2019).

Furthermore, as cited in Bai and Veall (2023), stated that some studies that use cross-state variation for the US include Horn et al. (2017), which found no effect of the minimum wage on mental health for men (but some for women), and Andreyeva and Ukert (2018), who found associated improvements in mental health for some groups, including those with lower levels of education, and whose dependent variable is the number of days that the group experiences mental health problems. Less days of absence are also seen by Du and Leigh (2018), who link this to improvements in health, particularly those brought on by psychosocial variables. While Kronenberg et al. (2017) and Maxwell et al. (2022) which examined the 2016, 2017, and 2018 increased in the UK minimum wage, as opposed to its introduction in 1998 did not found a significant association between the UK national minimum wage and the mental health of low wage workers, Reeves et al. (2017) estimated a reduction in the probability of mental health problems along with higher wages due to the UK national minimum wage. Filipinos are generally dissatisfied, not only because of terrible economic situations (unemployment, low wages, etc.), but also because of demands from family and society, thus the Philippines is a developing country that struggles to achieve economic stability due to outdated traditions that result in gaps in mental health promotion, which bleed into the economy. The

rising incidence of mental diseases has a significant impact on personal, societal, and economic capital. (Maravilla and Tan, 2021).

Moreover, this study will analyze the differences in Mental Health and Job Satisfaction of above minimum wage earners and minimum wage earners. The findings of this study will be used as the basis for the Mental Health and Job Satisfaction Program among above minimum wage earners and minimum wage earners that is called “Above and Minimum: A Comparative Study on the Mental Health and Job Satisfaction among Wage Earners”.

Research Questions

This study sought to investigate Mental Health, and Job Satisfaction among Above Minimum Wage Earners and Minimum Wage Earners. This study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. How may the respondent’s mental health be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. anxiety;
 - 1.2. depression;
 - 1.3. behavioral control; and
 - 1.4. positive affect?
2. How may the respondent’s job satisfaction be described in terms of:
 - 2.1. intrinsic
 - 2.2. extrinsic; and
 - 2.3. general satisfaction?
3. Is there a significant difference between the mental health of above minimum wage earners and minimum wage earners?
4. Is there a significant difference between the job satisfaction of above minimum wage earners and minimum wage earners?
5. What program may be made based on the outcome of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a comparative research design to identify the differences in Mental Health, and Job Satisfaction between Above Minimum Wage Earners and Minimum Wage Earners. Essentially, comparative research compares two groups to derive conclusions about them. Researchers attempt to identify and analyze differences between groups, and these comparative studies are most frequently cross-national. Comparative studies can be used to increase cultural and societal comprehension and lay the groundwork for compromise and cooperation, (Richardson, 2018). Therefore, the result of the two variables in two different groups will be compared and analyzed to know if there are differences in their mental health and job satisfaction.

Respondents

The total population is 192, and using the Slovin's formula, the researchers have a total sample size of 153 respondents. Ellen (2020), stated that when studying a whole population is difficult, a smaller sample is gathered through a random sampling technique. Slovin's formula enables a researcher to collect data on the population with the required level of precision. Slovin's formula informs the researcher about the sample size required to assure reasonable accuracy of results. With a sample size of 60 for above minimum wage earners and 93 for minimum wage earners employed in Valenzuela City. Moreover, the respondents will be through convenience sampling technique. According to Simkus (2023), convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling technique in which researchers select their sample only on the basis of convenience. Also it gathers data from a readily available and accessible population. The sample is made up of people who are most easily accessible to the researcher rather than people who are most representative of the population as a whole. With non-probability sampling, the sample is chosen by the researchers rather than drawn at random, meaning that only some members of the population have the same chance of taking part in the research. Convenience sampling is preferred by many researchers because it has few rules and enables them to quickly generate large samples. Hence, the following are the process of selecting respondents:

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>n</i>
Above Minimum Wage	70	60
Minimum Wage	122	93

Instrument

This study utilized two standardized quantitative research instruments in gathering the statistical data. The instruments are described as follows:

Mental Health Inventory (MHI)

Mental Health Inventory (MHI) was developed by Veit and Ware (1983). Mental Health Inventory is a widely accepted measure of emotional function as a whole. The 18-item version of the MHI is relatively concise, dependable, and maintains the subscale structure. The MHI has 4 subscales (Anxiety, Depression, Behavioral Control, and Positive Affect) and 1 total score. The subscale and total

scores range from 0-100, with higher scores indicating better mental health. Cronbach's alpha for the long form of the MHI is 0.93, while the short form has an alpha of 0.82. According to the National Multiple Sclerosis Society (2023) the MHI has been studied a lot in large groups of people, and there is a lot of proof that it works.

For the Anxiety Subscale, item number 10 assign raw scores are; All of the time (1)= 6, Most of the time (2) = 5, A good bit of the time (3) = 4, Some of the time (4) = 3, A little of the time (5) = 2, and None of the time (6) = 1. Meanwhile, there is no conversion needed for items number 4, 6, 11, and 18. For the Depression Subscale, no conversion of raw scores is needed. Thus, the Behavior Control Subscale, the assign raw scores to items number 5 and 8 are; All of the time (1) = 6, Most of the time (2) = 5, A good bit of the time (3) = 4, Some of the time (4) = 3, A little of the time (5) = 2, and None of the time (6) = 1.

However no conversion is needed for items 16 and 17. Lastly, for the Positive Affect Subscale, assign raw scores to items number 1, 7, 13 and 15 are; All of the time (1) = 6, Most of the time (2) = 5, A good bit of the time (3) = 4, Some of the time (4) = 3, A little of the time (5) = 2, and None of the time (6) = 1.

Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ)

The Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) was developed by Weiss, Dawis, England & Lofquist in 1967 (Yu et al., 2021). The MSQ is used to measure the satisfaction of an individual to their job. It is a questionnaire that contains 20 questions about the intrinsic, extrinsic and general satisfaction of minimum wage earners and above minimum wage earners. The scale is a five-point Likert scale that ranges from 1 (Very Dissatisfied) to 5 (Very Satisfied). In accordance to (Yu et al., 2021), The Cronbach's alphas of the original version's ranges are 0.84–0.91, 0.77–0.82, and 0.87–0.92 for intrinsic, extrinsic, and general. AS Vocational Psychology Research (2023) stated that the purpose of the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) is to find out how pleased an employee is with his or her job. There are three forms: two long forms (from 1977 and 1967) and one short form. Moreover, APA PsychNet Direct (2023) concluded that the MSQ gives more specific information than other measures of job satisfaction about the parts of a job that make a person happy. The Short Form was created to measure both intrinsic and extrinsic aspects of job satisfaction. Intrinsic job satisfaction refers to how individuals feel about the nature of the job activities themselves, whereas extrinsic job satisfaction refers to how individuals feel about external components of the work setting. Participants were asked to rate their level of satisfaction with statements such as "The opportunities to work alone." In this model, higher total scores indicate higher satisfaction with work. (Yu et al., 2021) Additionally, Lakatamitou noted that the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire "short form" (MSQ-short) is a self-report questionnaire that examines multiple dimensions of perceptions of teamwork and job satisfaction within healthcare settings, respectively (Bello et al., 2020).

Procedure

The aim of this study is to analyze the differences in mental health and job satisfaction between above minimum wage earners and minimum wage earners. With the help of Google Scholar, Google, Research Gate, and other web-based platforms, the researchers were able to gather information from publications, research papers, and specialized journals that will allow them to make more in-depth research findings.

The whole data collection process of this study was done online. Primarily, the call for the respondents was through the Human Resource Manager of the company. Afterward, a secured Google form was developed and given out to minimum wage earners and above minimum wage earners who are willing to participate. To avoid uncertainties, the respondents have read the consent and instructions thoroughly before starting the assessment. For the first part, the respondents answered the Mental Health Inventory (MHI) within more or less 10 minutes. In measuring their job satisfaction, the respondents started answering the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ), which took ten (10) minutes on average.

Following the ethical standards, confidentiality was assured throughout the process. The individual scores of the respondents were not given to anyone and were used for academic purposes only.

Data Analysis

The data was tabulated and processed using Microsoft excel. The statistical techniques that will be used include;

Mean. The mean, also known as the arithmetic mean of a dataset, is obtained by dividing the sum of all values by the total number of values. The measure of central tendency known as the "average" is widely used and considered the most popular (Bhandari, 2020).

Interval Approach. A confidence interval is the mean of your estimate plus and minus its variation. Within a specific level of confidence, this is the range of values you expect your estimate to fall between if you redo the test (Bevans, 2023).

Variance. A statistical measurement of the dispersion between values in a data collection. Variance explicitly assesses how far each number in the set is from the mean, and consequently from every other number in the set (Hayes, 2023).

Z-test. The z-test is a statistical method used to compare or find the significance of several statistical measures, especially the mean in a sample from a community with a normal distribution or between two separate samples. More than 30 people were used in the sample for the Z-test, which is the most common statistical tool used in research methods (Sapkota,2023).

Ethical Considerations

The current study will seek approval from research adviser for the proposed data gathering process. The strict ethical principles will be observed to guarantee that the approval is granted.

The participants will be given a consent form before the data gathering process starts. The respondents will be clarified regarding their voluntary involvement with the data gathering. Participants are aware of their rights before conducting data gathering, and respondents are aware of the reason why their personal information will be used. Confidentiality of the respondents will also be discussed, respondents are protected under the Republic Act 10173, also known as Data Privacy Act (DPA).

Strict measures were put together to protect data confidentiality. The researchers preserved the information acquired from and about the respondents throughout the research for study record-keeping purposes, and it will be discarded once the research report is completed. The names and other personally identifiable information of the participants were kept confidential and separate from the study data. Except in cases where the researcher is obligated by law to report specific incidents, participant data will be kept totally confidential. The study's findings may be published in an article or presented in a presentation, but no information identifying the participants will be included.

Results and Discussion

This section answers the questions that were specified in the statement of problem. This part of the study summarizes the statistical results and the findings out of the gathered data.

Mental Health

Table 1. *The Descriptive Analysis of Mental Health Anxiety among Above Minimum Wage Earners and Minimum Wage Earners*

Anxiety	Above Minimum			Minimum		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
4.How much of the time have you been a very nervous person?	3.58	0.98	Good	3.23	1.18	Bad
6. How much of the time have you felt tense or high-strung?	3.7	1.09	Good	3.49	1.07	Bad
11.How much of the time have you felt restless, fidgety, or impatient?	3.4	1.04	Bad	3.40	0.99	Bad
18.How much of the time have you been anxious or worried?	3.05	1.16	Bad	3.26	1.02	Bad
10. How much of the time were you able to relax without difficulty?	3.43	1.17	Bad	3.42	1.19	Bad
Weighted Mean	3.43	1.09	Bad	3.36	1.09	Bad

Legend: 1.00-1.83 = Very Bad, 1.84-2.66 = Rather Bad, 2.67-3.49 = Bad, 3.50-4.32 Rather Good, 4.33 – 5.15 = Good, 5.16 -5.98 = Very Good.

Table 1 shows that individuals, regardless of their income, are experiencing significant levels of anxiety at work. The highest mean scores, rated as 'good,' are consistent for those earning above the minimum wage (3.7) as well as those earning at the minimum wage (3.49). In addition, the weighted mean for individuals in both income brackets, above the minimum wage (3.43) and at the minimum wage (3.36), aligns similarly, indicating as 'bad'. This suggests that both above minimum wage earners and minimum wage earners are experiencing anxiety. To support that Pindar (2023) stated that anxiety in the workplace affects employees at all income levels, influencing their concerns about job performance, financial stability, and interpersonal relationships at work.

The findings supported by the study of Bryson et al. (2012), shows that higher salary is linked to increased job satisfaction and anxiety at work, even after taking into consideration the amount of work that employees put out, this relationship is still strong. When employees are being paid more, employees often feel under pressure to perform better, which tends to increase anxiety.

Correspondingly, Stewart (2021), has found that some low-wage workers still have anxieties about a federal wage increase, despite recognizing the challenges of living on low wages and knowing that their lives and those of their coworkers would be much better on a more livable wage. The supported studies means that regardless of wage earners' income level, they still experience significant levels of anxiety at work.

The data in Table 2 shows that individuals earning above the minimum wage indicate they feel somewhat better, with a mean score of 3.62. On the other hand, those at the minimum wage scored lower at 3.4 falling in the 'bad' range. However, when considering the overall picture including how these scores are distributed among wage earners, the situation changes.

The combined weighted mean for those above the minimum wage drops to 3.62, still considered 'good', but for those at the minimum wage, the weighted mean falls more significantly to 3.39, which is classified as 'bad'. This suggests that the minimum wage earners have a higher possibility of experiencing depression compared to the above minimum wage earners, since the above minimum wage

earners score good in the depression.

Table 2. *The Descriptive Analysis of Mental Health Depression among Above Minimum Wage Earners and Minimum Wage Earners*

Depression	Above Minimum			Minimum		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
2. How much of the time did you feel depressed?	3.48	1.32	Bad	3.47	1.21	Bad
9. How much of the time have you felt downhearted and blue?	3.6	1.19	Good	3.35	1.27	Bad
12. How much of the time have you been moody, or brooded about things?	3.75	1.11	Good	3.48	1.17	Bad
14. How much of the time have you been in low or very low spirits?	3.72	1.09	Good	3.32	1.17	Bad
3. How much of the time have you felt loved and wanted?	3.55	1.11	Good	3.37	1.18	Bad
Weighted Mean	3.62	1.17	Good	3.4	1.20	Bad

Legend: 1.00-1.83 = Very Bad, 1.84-2.66 = Rather Bad, 2.67-3.49 = Bad, 3.50-4.32 Rather Good, 4.33 - 5.15 = Good, 5.16 -5.98 = Very Good.

The findings support the study of Zare et al. (2022) found that more severe symptoms were associated with lower income. Specifically, in terms of severity, individuals from low-income groups were 4.5 times more depressed compared to high-income earners, same as the individuals who belong to the middle income groups indicate that they have suffered depressions approximately 5 times more often. Correspondingly, Bai and Veall (2023) found that higher minimum wage in the provinces of Canada decreased the probability of mental distress and depression among low-educated workers. In addition, Taylor et al. (2011) assert that psychological well-being may have been most negatively impacted by income variations since poverty is known to cause financial strain, which is a recognized predictor of major depression.

Table 3. *The Descriptive Analysis of Mental Health Behavioral Control among Above Minimum Wage Earners and Minimum Wage Earners*

Behavioral Control	Above Minimum			Minimum		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
16. How much of the time did you feel you had nothing to look forward to?	3.7	0.98	Good	3.53	1.18	Good
17. How much of the time have you felt so down in the dumps that nothing could cheer you up?	3.68	1.23	Good	3.46	1.07	Bad
5. How much of the time have you been in firm control of your behavior, thoughts, emotions, feelings?	3.35	1.10	Bad	3.38	1.04	Bad
8. How much of the time have you felt emotionally stable?	3.77	1.32	Good	3.34	1.06	Bad
Weighted Mean	3.63	1.16	Good	3.43	1.09	Bad

Legend: 1.00-1.83 = Very Bad, 1.84-2.66 = Rather Bad, 2.67-3.49 = Bad, 3.50-4.32 Rather Good, 4.33 - 5.15 = Good, 5.16 -5.98 = Very Good.

Based on the information provided in Table 3, individuals earning above the minimum wage attained a highest score of 3.68, falling within the 'good' range. Conversely, those earning at the minimum wage achieved a highest score of 3.53, also categorized as 'good'. Moreover, the weighted mean score for individuals above the minimum wage stood at 3.63, classified as 'good', while for minimum wage earners, the weighted mean score was 3.43, falling into the 'bad' category. This result indicates that the above minimum wage earners have a good behavioral control compared to the minimum wage earners.

These support the American Psychological Association (2023), which suggests that employees with strong behavioral control typically manage stress effectively, deal with problems at work with ease, and interact pleasantly with their employers and coworkers. This develops an accepting and cooperative environment in addition to increasing productivity, this control manifests itself in a variety of ways, such as adhering to corporate policies, conducting oneself with dignity, speaking clearly, and acting with self-control in the workplace.

For Table 4, individuals prefer experiencing positive emotions and engaging in constructive interactions with others and the difficulties of life. The above minimum wage earners highest score is 3.52 that is interpreted as good. On the other hand, the minimum wage earner's highest score is 3.75 which is interpreted as good.

In addition, the total mean for above minimum wage earners is 3.47 which is interpreted as bad compared to the minimum average earners that is interpreted as good with 3.56 total mean. Filiz and Adam's (2018) findings reveal that the minimum wage has a

considerable positive influence on all categories of well-being, with a rise in life satisfaction. According to Kuroki (2021) the findings suggest that higher minimum wages may have a positive impact on mental health, especially for men, by reducing the average number of bad mental health days.

Table 4. The Descriptive Analysis of Mental Health Positive Affect among Above Minimum Wage Earners and Minimum Wage Earners

Positive Affect	Above Minimum			Minimum		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. How much of the time has your daily life been full of things that were interesting to you?	3.52	1.25	Good	3.32	1.13	Bad
7. How much of the time have you felt calm and peaceful?	3.42	0.99	Bad	3.72	1.09	Good
13. How much of the time have you ever felt cheerful, light-hearted?	3.48	1.27	Bad	3.75	1.06	Good
15. How much of the time were you a happy person?	3.47	1.17	Bad	3.44	1.04	Bad
Weighted Mean	3.47	1.17	Bad	3.56	1.08	Good

Legend: 1.00-1.83 = Very Bad, 1.84-2.66 = Rather Bad, 2.67-3.49 = Bad, 3.50-4.32 Rather Good, 4.33 – 5.15 = Good, 5.16 -5.98 = Very Good.

Meanwhile, Leigh and Du stated that product price increases do not generally affect product quality, but salary increases may improve job quality by raising worker morale, lowering turnover, and increasing productivity. Some economists claim that an increase in wages can be compensated by an increase in quality, such that employers would not feel compelled to reduce the number of employees or hours worked if the minimum wage increased.

Table 5. The Summary of the Difference in the Mental Health between Above Minimum Wage Earners and Minimum Wage Earners

Subscales	Above Minimum			Minimum		
	Mean	SD	Ver. Inter	Mean	SD	Ver. Inter
Anxiety	3.43	1.09	Bad	3.36	1.09	Bad
Depression	3.62	1.17	Good	3.4	1.20	Bad
Behavioral Control	3.63	1.16	Good	3.43	1.09	Bad
Positive Affect	3.47	1.17	Bad	3.56	1.08	Good

The Descriptive Analysis of the Comparison in Mental Health between Above Minimum Wage Earners and Above Minimum Wage Earners

The summary of mental health, which results in the minimum wage earners getting a lower mean score compared to those who earn above minimum wage. The result indicates that the above minimum wage earners have a good mental health compared to the minimum wage earners.

Lower educated workers' chances of experiencing mental distress and depression were linked to higher minimum wages in Canada's provinces. Overall, the findings indicate that in Canada, a 10 percent increase in the minimum wage would be linked to a statistically significant decrease in the incidence of depression and distress of the order of 0.3 percentage points.

However, there is evidence to support a much stronger relationship between the two outcomes for men and some evidence suggesting a smaller effect, particularly at high levels of distress (Bai & Veall, 2023). It indicates that increasing the minimum wage may help ease financial troubles while also lowering the level of mental and emotional issues in this demographic. The data support the idea that economic hardship and financial strain are contributing to the growth in extreme distress. Policies such as raising the minimum wage, which address these economic variables, have the potential to improve mental health outcomes for vulnerable people.

Job Satisfaction

According to the findings in Table 6, the highest score for intrinsic job satisfaction among above-minimum wage earners is 3.59, understood as high, while the highest score for minimum wage earners is 3.63, interpreted also as high. Furthermore, the weighted mean for above-minimum-wage earners is 3.43, which is considered as high, whereas the weighted mean for minimum-wage earners is 3.39, which is interpreted as moderate.

This indicates that the above minimum wage earners have a high intrinsic satisfaction compared to the minimum wage earners. Employees are more likely to be intrinsically motivated if they are given opportunities for both career and personal growth (Abu-Tineh et al., 2023). Also, employees are more likely to be satisfied with their jobs when they are given the freedom to make decisions and exercise their creativity (Gözükara & Olakolu, 2016). This is particularly relevant for wage earners, as intrinsic job satisfaction, which arises from personal growth opportunities and prospects for advancement.

Table 6. *The Descriptive Analysis of Intrinsic Job Satisfaction among Above Minimum Wage*

Intrinsic	Above Minimum			Minimum		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. This is how I feel about being able to keep busy all the time.	3.48	0.98	High	3.44	1.03	High
2. This is how I feel about the chance to work alone on the job.	3.28	1.11	Moderate	3.45	1.01	High
3. This is how I feel about the chance to do different things from time to time.	3.46	1.03	High	3.43	0.98	High
4. This is how I feel about the chance to be somebody in the community.	3.34	1.01	Moderate	3.28	0.99	Moderate
7. This is how I feel about being able to do things that don't go against my conscience.	3.34	1.12	Moderate	3.43	0.93	High
8. This is how I feel about the way my job provides for steady employment.	3.59	0.97	High	3.63	0.95	High
9. This is how I feel about the chance to do things for other people.	3.52	1.06	High	3.33	0.97	Moderate
10. This is how I feel about the chance to tell people what to do.	3.29	0.97	Moderate	3.41	1.09	High
Q11. This is how I feel about the chance to do something that makes use of my abilities.	3.52	0.99	High	3.46	1.05	High
Q15. This is how I feel about the freedom to use my own judgment.	3.48	0.87	High	3.32	1.07	Moderate
Q16. This is how I feel about the chance to try my own methods of doing the job.	3.56	1.07	High	3.28	0.95	Moderate
Q20. This is the feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.	3.31	1.04	Moderate	3.26	1.06	Moderate
Weighted Mean	3.43	1.02	High	3.39	1.01	Moderate

Legend: 1.00-1.80 = Very low, 1.81-2.60 = Low, 2.61-3.40 = Moderate, 3.41-4.20 High, 4.21 – 5.00 Very High

Under Table 7, the highest score in extrinsic job satisfaction among above-minimum wage earners is 3.57, which is considered as high, while the highest mean among minimum wage earners is 3.59, which is interpreted as high. Furthermore, the weighted mean for above minimum wage is 3.41, which is interpreted as high, however the weighted mean for minimum wage is 3.4, which is interpreted as moderate. When wages are higher, people tend to be more satisfied with their jobs (Medgyesi & Zólyomi, 2016).

Table 7. *The Descriptive Analysis of Extrinsic Job Satisfaction among Above Minimum Wage Earners and Minimum Wage Earners*

Extrinsic	Above Minimum			Minimum		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
5. This is how I feel about the way my boss handles his/her workers.	3.54	0.94	High	3.23	1.03	Moderate
6. This is how I feel about the competence of my supervisor in making decisions.	3.31	1.06	Moderate	3.31	1.11	Moderate
12. This is how I feel about the way company policies are put into practice.	3.34	1.09	Moderate	3.27	1.06	Moderate
13. This is how I feel about my pay and the amount of work I do.	3.29	1.12	Moderate	3.59	0.94	High
14. This is how I feel about the chances for advancement on this job.	3.57	0.96	High	3.46	1.05	High
19. This is how I feel about the praise I get for doing a good job.	3.41	0.96	High	3.52	0.91	High
Weighted Mean	3.41	1.02	High	3.4	1.02	Moderate

Legend: 1.00-1.80 = Very low, 1.81-2.60 = Low, 2.61-3.40 = Moderate, 3.41-4.20 High, 4.21 – 5.00 Very High

The impact on job satisfaction was primarily noticed among employees who perceived themselves as being influenced by the minimum wage, compared to employees who were objectively affected. This emphasizes the significance of effectively expressing the favorable effects of raising the minimum wage to workers, with the aim of fostering their recognition and value of the salary increase (Bossler & Broszeit, 2017). This aligns with the weighted mean extrinsic job satisfaction observed among above-minimum wage earners compared to minimum wage earners.

Table 8 shows individual experience, and the sources of satisfaction or discontent vary among professional groups. Work surroundings, job performance, and mental health conditions are often connected with general contentment. The highest mean for above-minimum-wage earners is 3.59, which is considered as high. The highest mean for minimum wage earners, on the other hand, is 3.63, which is considered as high. Furthermore, the overall mean for above minimum wage earners is 3.42, which is viewed as high when compared

to the total mean for minimum wage earners, which is interpreted as moderate with 3.4.

Table 8. *The Descriptive Analysis of General Job Satisfaction among Above Minimum Wage Earners and Minimum Wage Earners*

General Satisfaction	Above Minimum			Minimum		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. This is how I feel about being able to keep busy all the time.	3.48	0.98	High	3.44	1.03	High
2. This is how I feel about the chance to work alone on the job.	3.28	1.11	Moderate	3.45	1.01	High
3. This is how I feel about the chance to do different things from time to time.	3.46	1.03	High	3.43	0.98	High
4. This is how I feel about the chance to be somebody in the community.	3.34	1.01	Moderate	3.28	0.99	Moderate
5. This is how I feel about the way my boss handles his/her workers.	3.54	0.94	High	3.23	1.03	Moderate
6. This is how I feel about the competence of my supervisor in making decisions.	3.31	1.06	Moderate	3.31	1.11	Moderate
7. This is how I feel about being able to do things that don't go against my conscience.	3.34	1.12	Moderate	3.43	0.93	High
8. This is how I feel about the way my job provides for steady employment.	3.59	0.97	High	3.63	0.95	High
9. This is how I feel about the chance to do things for other people.	3.52	1.06	High	3.33	0.97	Moderate
10. This is how I feel about the chance to tell people what to do.	3.29	0.97	Moderate	3.41	1.09	High
Q11. This is how I feel about the chance to do something that makes use of my abilities.	3.52	0.99	High	3.46	1.05	High
12. This is how I feel about the way company policies are put into practice.	3.34	1.09	Moderate	3.27	1.06	Moderate
13. This is how I feel about my pay and the amount of work I do.	3.29	1.12	Moderate	3.59	0.94	High
14. This is how I feel about the chances for advancement on this job.	3.57	0.96	High	3.46	1.05	High
Q15. This is how I feel about the freedom to use my own judgment.	3.48	0.87	High	3.32	1.07	Moderate
Q16. This is how I feel about the chance to try my own methods of doing the job.	3.56	1.07	High	3.28	0.95	Moderate
Q17. This is how I feel about the working conditions.	3.33	1.03	Moderate	3.59	0.96	High
Q18. This is how I feel about the way my co-workers get along with each other.	3.34	1.09	Moderate	3.43	0.96	High
19. This is how I feel about the praise I get for doing a good job.	3.41	0.96	High	3.52	0.91	High
Q20. This is the feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.	3.31	1.04	Moderate	3.26	1.06	Moderate
Weighted Mean	3.42	1.02	High	3.4	1.01	Moderate

Legend: 1.00-1.80 = Very low, 1.81-2.60 = Low, 2.61-3.40 = Moderate, 3.41-4.20 High, 4.21 – 5.00 Very High

Studies from the Society for Human Resource Management (2020) and others show the direct relationship between employer recognition, employee happiness, and employees' growing desire for higher pay and better benefits.

Table 9. *The Summary of the Difference in the Job Satisfaction between Above Minimum Wage Earners and Minimum Wage Earners*

Subscales	Above Minimum			Minimum		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Intrinsic	3.43	1.02	High	3.39	1.01	Moderate
Extrinsic	3.41	1.02	High	3.4	1.02	Moderate
General Satisfaction	3.42	1.02	High	3.4	1.01	Moderate

This table presents a summary of job satisfaction, indicating that individuals earning above the minimum wage had a higher mean score in comparison to those earning the minimum wage even though there are small differences.. The study of Storer and Reich (2019), emphasizes the need of taking into factors such as position and duration when determining the influence of minimum wage regulations on job satisfaction. For low-wage workers who have been with the company for less than a year, higher minimum salaries can lead to better job satisfaction. Long-term and slightly higher-status employees, on the contrary, may suffer decreasing job satisfaction as a

result of wage compression caused by minimum wage hikes. On average, those who earn minimum wages tend to experience lower levels of job satisfaction (Pohlig et al., 2020). This strengthens the findings that those earning the minimum wage tend to be less satisfied with their jobs than those earning above minimum wage and the duration of minimum wage can affect the job satisfaction of the employees.

Table 10. *Statistical Analysis of Mental Health Differences between Minimum Wage Earners and Above Minimum Wage Earners*

Variables	\bar{x}	z-stat	z-crit (two-tailed)	P-value	Decision
Minimum Wage Earners	3.4375				
Above Minimum Wage Earners	3.5375	1.530	1.960	0.126	Accept the Null Hypothesis

According to the study of Kuroki (2021), there is no difference between state minimum salaries and high levels of suffering among low-income, prime-age Americans with no college education. A 10% rise in the minimum wage is connected with a 0.4-0.5 percentage point decrease in the likelihood of experiencing acute discomfort. Several studies have found that minimum income is associated with mental illness, including depression. A population-based longitudinal study, for example, discovered that most mental health conditions were connected with minimum levels of income, and participants with a family income of less than \$20,000 per year were at an elevated risk of incident mood disorders (Sareen et al., 2011). Furthermore, Li et al. (2022) found that the relationship between income and mental health is U-shaped, meaning that depression declines as income increases at the lower-income level, but beyond a certain threshold, further increases in income can have significant mental health costs.

On the other hand, while a high-paying job can provide financial security, it can also damage mental health. Studies of older European workers have shown that job quality has an impact on mental health, whereas job uncertainty has a small but significant impact on mental health (Henseke, 2018). According to Psychology Magazine (2023) 88% of Indian employees are willing to give up high-paying professions for the sake of their mental health, with excessive work hours being a major contributor to work-related stress. A report from CBS Interactive (2010), certain high-stress and high-stakes jobs, often associated with high pay, have been identified as more prone to burnout and depression. Additionally, a survey of over 5,000 employees discovered that 83% felt emotionally drained from work, and 71% firmly agreed that the workplace has an impact on their mental health (Caron, 2023).

Hence, the results indicate that mental health difficulties, such as depression, aren't confined solely to those with lower or minimum incomes. Although several studies found that there is often a correlation between lower income levels and increased mental health struggles, these challenges are also experienced by individuals in higher-paying positions. Income alone doesn't determine mental well-being; rather, factors like work-related stress, satisfaction in one's job, access to healthcare, and the overall work environment play substantial roles in influencing mental health. Consequently, mental well-being is not solely determined by income but is shaped by a combination of socioeconomic circumstances and individual factors.

Table 11. *Statistical Analysis of Job Satisfaction Differences between Minimum Wage Earners and Above Minimum Wage Earners*

Variables	\bar{x}	z-stat	z-crit (two-tailed)	P-value	Decision
Minimum Wage Earners	3.40				
Above Minimum Wage Earners	3.42	0.009	1.960	0.993	Accept the Null Hypothesis

Table 11 demonstrates that there is no significant difference in job satisfaction between individuals earning the minimum wage and those earning above the minimum wage. By utilizing the z-test to examine the two sample means, it is observed that the z-statistic of 0.009 does not exceed the critical value of z in a two-tailed test of 1.960. This outcome indicates that the result is not statistically significant. Further evidence that the result is not statistically significant is provided by the fact that the p-value of 0.992615 is higher than the limit of 0.05, which can be considered the level of significance. Consequently, the researchers will accept the null hypothesis, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference in job satisfaction between minimum wage earners and above minimum wage.

The relationship between wages and job satisfaction is a complex and nuanced subject. According to research, increased earnings can lead to greater job satisfaction. According to a Harvard University study, companies are aware of the possible benefits of paying

employees more than their competitors, such as fewer turnover, increased worker effort, and improved recruitment (Emanuel & Harrington, 2020). Furthermore, the study by Güral and Ayaita (2020) revealed that the implementation of a minimum wage resulted in a significant improvement in well-being, including life happiness, job satisfaction, and pay satisfaction among low earnings.

In summary, the data suggests that higher pay, especially increases in the minimum wage, can improve job satisfaction among low-income employees. However, the relationship between wages and job happiness is influenced by various circumstances, and the household context may also play a role in low-wage workers' job satisfaction (Pohlig et al., 2020).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

The results reveal widespread mental health challenges among both above-minimum-wage and minimum-wage earners, emphasizing the need for interventions. Despite slightly lower anxiety levels, both groups exhibit worrisome levels, with above-minimum-wage earners reporting higher depression scores. Poor behavioral control and low positive affect across income levels underscore the importance of addressing emotional well-being.

Overall, job satisfaction is high for both income groups, with slightly better scores for those above the minimum wage. Intrinsic satisfaction is notably higher for higher earners, emphasizing the role of income in life satisfaction. Extrinsic factors contribute to job satisfaction, with a positive outlook for both groups. In conclusion, the research underscores the significance of intrinsic and extrinsic factors in creating a positive work environment, offering valuable insights for employers and policymakers.

Contrary to expectations, no statistically significant difference in mental health is found between income groups. This challenges assumptions about the impact of income on mental well-being. While both minimum-wage and above-minimum-wage earners report high job satisfaction, the study supports the hypothesis of statistically significant differences in satisfaction between the groups. Recognizing the influence of both intrinsic and extrinsic elements is crucial for developing strategies that enhance overall well-being and job satisfaction.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

In order to address the specific challenges identified in the study, such as general poor mental health conditions and issues related to anxiety, depression, behavioral control, and positive affect, human resources personnel should design and implement comprehensive mental health interventions. Initiatives designed to help people in both income categories manage their stress and exercise better self-control. Since both groups performed poorly in this area, coping mechanisms and stress resilience could be improved through training programs, workshops, or counseling services. Investigate and put into practice methods to improve overall emotional well-being and positive affect in the workplace. This could include employee recognition programs, workshops on mental health, and workplace initiatives that foster a positive and supportive environment.

It is recommended that the organization educate employers regarding the mental health difficulties that their staff, regardless of socioeconomic status, may encounter. Employers should be trained to identify indicators of mental health concerns in order to reduce stigma and foster a supportive work environment. Offer managers specialized training in the areas of communication, supportive leadership, and mental health awareness. Providing managers with the necessary resources to identify indicators of mental health concerns and react with empathy can foster a more nurturing organizational environment.

The human resources personnel should find out how well employee wellness programs are doing to improve workers' emotional and psychological health and overall happiness on the job. Find ways to enhance or expand current programs so they can better meet the varied needs of the workforce by assessing their impact.

Implement the program entitled "Workplace Wellbeing: The keys to Mental Health and Job Satisfaction" that will help the employees to gain knowledge about the topic and this might help them to have a good mental health and job satisfaction.

Further studies can be carried out in the future to pinpoint the precise elements that influence job satisfaction in people making more than the minimum wage. A deeper comprehension of these variables can help customize policies and interventions for optimal effect. In order to monitor changes in job satisfaction over time, they can also carry out longitudinal studies. An understanding of the long-term consequences of workplace interventions, prevailing economic conditions, and other external factors can be gained by tracking changes in job satisfaction.

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